

Review

Advancing digital depth: AI-enhanced 3D reconstruction for post-harvest food supply chain quality management

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ABSTRACT

Traditional computer vision-based quality perception lacks depth information, limiting its application to reliable food quality management in the post-harvest supply chain. Three-dimensional (3D) reconstruction technology captures detailed surface geometry and internal structural information for reliable non-destructive quality inspection. Combined with emerging artificial intelligence (AI) technologies, 3D data-driven adaptive management brings potential for next-generation post-harvest quality management. This review analyzed 90 major related studies during 2015–2025, covering high-throughput 3D in-line inspection, high-resolution tomography, portable 3D sensing, and AI-driven 3D reconstruction technologies. Post-harvest supply chain application scenarios are mainly distributed in post-harvest processing (33 studies), manufacturing (29 studies), distribution (15 studies), and consumption (13 studies). Among them, fruit and vegetable products are the most intensively researched, highlighting the suitability and potential benefits of 3D reconstruction for these types of products. Besides, multiple 3D reconstruction technologies have been validated for postharvest evaluation, with X-ray CT dominating postharvest processing, manufacturing, and distribution, and portable RGB imaging devices dominating application in consumption. Besides, relevant 3D reconstruction analysis is evolving from geometry-driven to AI-enhanced analysis and management, highlighting the growing role of 3D reconstruction technology in intelligent, traceable, and sustainable post-harvest supply chain quality management. In the future, by integrating digital twins, IoT, and blockchain technologies, it is expected to build a transparent, tamper-proof quality traceability and control system across the global food supply chain.

1. Introduction

The rapid globalisation and continuous growth of the world population have significantly intensified the demand for reliable and high-quality supply chains, particularly in the food industry. Meanwhile, food safety has emerged as a critical global concern that directly affects human health, economic stability, and social development. Consequently, modern consumers are placing increasing emphasis on the consistent high quality and safety of food products (Sharma et al., 2024). Given that the food supply chain consists of multiple stages from farm to fork, quality control operations are essential for enhancing the performance of the food supply chain and maintaining product integrity and safety. However, challenges related to food quality and safety frequently arise due to various factors, including defective raw materials,

inadequate manufacturing controls, cross-contamination, food fraud, packaging failures, improper storage, and consumer mishandling. Therefore, the food supply chain must be carefully managed at every step to maintain quality. Otherwise, failures at any stage can propagate throughout the supply chain, affecting multiple companies, countries, and the safety of thousands of individuals. However, quality control presents a complex challenge due to the vast array of product types and quality-related variables that need to be evaluated and carefully managed across different stages (Ziani et al., 2025).

To address these challenges and mitigate risks, numerous regulatory frameworks and management measures have been implemented across all stages of the food supply chain. These include Good Agricultural Practices (GAPs) at the production stages, Hazard Analysis and Critical Control Points (HACCP) during processing, cold chain logistics

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optimisation, food safety training, and international collaborations such as INFOSAN for outbreak alerts. Besides, at the technical level, advanced quality evaluation technologies such as spectroscopy, mass spectrometry (MS), high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS), and sensor-based systems have been applied to food quality management (Liu et al., 2025; Ziani et al., 2025). Despite their advances, achieving both high accuracy and efficiency remains challenging given the demand for rapid, non-destructive, and cost-effective quality inspection methods. For instance, although spectroscopic techniques are widely applied for quality evaluation due to their non-destructive, rapid analysis capabilities, they generally capture spectral information from limited viewpoints or surface areas, providing incomplete information on the overall structure or internal composition (Ren et al., 2022). Similarly, MS, HPLC, and GC-MS deliver precise chemical analyses but require destructive sampling, extensive preparation, and complex operation, limiting their real-time applicability in large-scale industrial and distribution settings. Generally, food supply chain quality management faces three obvious system-level challenges: time-sensitive, heterogeneous products, and environmental interference. In detail, time-sensitive demands high-throughput and real-time inspection capabilities to match dynamic processing and logistics flows. Heterogeneous food products exhibit diverse quality features, such as shape, texture, and composition, which require adaptive evaluation strategies. Additionally, environmental factors, including variations in illumination, product motion, temperature, or humidity, further interfere with consistent monitoring. Therefore, these challenges require spatially comprehensive, scenario-adaptive, and data-rich sensing methods that can provide comprehensive quality indicators for food products across the supply chain.

Computer vision has become one of the most reliable technologies for rapid, non-destructive quality inspection, and its evolution from two-dimensional (2D) to 3D analysis provides a transformative pathway toward resolving the above challenges (Yu et al., 2024). Compared with 2D vision, which is limited by viewing angles and the lack of depth information, 3D reconstruction provides more comprehensive information of both surface and internal characteristics, offering noticeable improvements in quality management within the food production chain. For instance, in raw material defect sorting, 3D reconstructed models provide complete surface detail to avoid occlusion problems from limited viewpoints, addressing the limitations inherent in 2D image-based analysis (Song et al., 2024). Unlike other standard industrial or medical products, food products often exhibit non-standardised shapes, compositional heterogeneity, and dynamic physicochemical changes at each step in the supply chain. These features complicate quality assessment based on 2D imaging or point-based spectroscopy, while 3D reconstruction is uniquely suited to capture volumetric, textural, and internal variations of food materials, providing critical information that directly relates to morphological features, sensory texture, and compositional attributes distribution (Sun et al., 2023; Verma et al., 2025; Withers et al., 2021). Furthermore, high-fidelity 3D reconstruction has the potential to serve as a valuable tool for product traceability and authenticity verification, ensuring that quality and safety standards are consistently maintained throughout the supply chain.

Furthermore, with the advancement of artificial intelligence (AI), 3D computer vision has entered a new stage of automation and intelligence, marking a core component of Food Industry 4.0. AI facilitates the learning and interpretation of complex 3D data through machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), enabling predictive modelling and adaptive control across different supply chain stages (Shi et al., 2025). ML as a fundamental subfield of AI empowers systems to develop predictive models using extensive datasets from sensors deployed

throughout the food supply chain, which are particularly effective for classification and regression tasks such as quality grading and parameter prediction (Nisbet et al., 2024; Song et al., 2024). As a more specialised branch of ML, DL primarily relies on artificial neural networks (ANNs). It excels at processing unstructured, high-dimensional datasets like 3D point clouds or volumetric data, capable of extracting hierarchical features that capture subtle quality variations (Shao et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2024). The application of AI has significantly expanded the scope and precision of food quality assessment by enabling accurate, real-time evaluation and enhancing adaptive decision-making capabilities throughout the entire food supply chain quality management process.

Despite the fast progress of 3D reconstruction and AI techniques in recent years, existing relevant reviews mainly focus on specific 3D reconstruction methods (Xiang and Wang, 2023), specific products (Lan et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2024), broader applications relevant to spatial calculation (Ma et al., 2024), or within agricultural scenarios (Yu et al., 2024). Given the varied quality control requirements across supply chain stages, fragmented coverage makes it difficult to translate these techniques into deployment decisions. Currently, there is a lack of comprehensive research systematically integrating the application of advanced 3D reconstruction techniques with product quality management in post-harvest food supply chains. In particular, there is a lack of work that unifies the core perceptual strategies, summarizes relevant food quality control applications, and explores the promising potential of AI-enhanced reconstruction mechanisms across post-harvest sectors.

Therefore, this review critically examines relevant research published mainly between 2015 and 2025, which aims to: (1) introduce the key principles and representative applications of relevant 3D reconstruction techniques, discuss their perception suitability, deployment constraints, and maturity in post-harvest supply chain management; (2) investigate typical applications of 3D reconstruction for quality control across post-harvest supply chain scenarios, and provide statistical maps across supply chain sections; (3) highlight the contribution of AI in 3D representation generation, and 3D data analysis, and provide a conceptual framework on AI-enabled 3D reconstruction for postharvest supply-chain quality management. Compared with existing studies, this review offers a supply chain oriented integration and proposes an AI-enhanced 3D reconstruction post-harvest food quality management framework, as well as decision-support guidance on instrument deployment.

2. Advanced 3D reconstruction sensors and methods

Building upon the conceptual overview of 3D reconstruction in post-harvest food supply chain quality management, this section examines the major sensing systems and reconstruction methods for 3D food product quality analysis. In general, 3D reconstruction in food quality control involves capturing spatial information to generate digital models, enabling the quantification of critical quality features, including physicochemical parameters, product morphological attributes, and microstructural information. Because food products exhibit high heterogeneity and diverse optical properties, and different stages of the food supply chain focus on distinct quality indicators, the choice of sensing and reconstruction methods greatly influences inspection accuracy, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness (Shi et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2024). Table 1 summarises the comparative characteristics of major 3D reconstruction technologies for food quality management, revealing a clear trade-off among resolution, speed, and reconstruction cost for different supply chain quality control scenarios. The structured-light and Time-of-Flight (ToF) systems show the highest industrial suitabilities, while X-ray computed tomography (X-ray CT), magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM), and optical coherence tomography (OCT) remain mainly laboratory-based reference

Table 1
Deployment-oriented comparison and decision-support guidance for 3D reconstruction techniques across post-harvest supply-chain quality control.

Techniques	Application Category*	Information depth	Typical 3D representation	General acquisition speed	Spatial resolution**	Cost range***	Computational load****	Technology maturity	Typical application in the supply chain	Deployment barriers
Structured light	C1	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	2–20 fps	Sub-millimeter scale	\$25–100k+	High	Industrial ready	At-line grading, defect detection, and packaging inspection	Transparent and specular surface sensitive, strict light control
ToF Camera	C1	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	5 – 60 fps	Millimeter scale	\$0.2–5k	Low	Industrial ready	Inline volume and mass estimation, packaging inspection	Multipath interference, depth bias drift
LiDAR	C1	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	10 – 20 fps	Millimetre to centimetre scale	\$5–40k	Medium	Industrial ready	At-line inspection, warehouse inventory, logistics monitoring	Limited detail, occlusion and alignment problem
3D HSI	C1	Surface, physicochemical		3–40 fps (snapshot)	Sub-millimeter scale	\$25–250k+	High	Pilot instrument	Sorting, compositional mapping, fraud detection	High cost, complex calibration, spectral-spatial trade-off
OCT	C2	Subsurface	Voxel	Less than 1 min/dataset	Micrometer scale	\$25–150k	High	Pilot instrument	Internal defect detection, package inspection, microstructure monitoring	High cost, limited sample size, motion artifacts problem
CLSM	C2	Subsurface	Voxel	0.1–2 min/dataset	Micrometer scale	\$500–900k	High	Lab proof of concept	Microstructural analysis, ingredient interaction R&D	Slow 3D stacks, photobleaching and phototoxicity effect
X-ray CT	C2	Internal	Voxel	10–120 min/dataset	Sub-micrometre scale	\$200–2 M	Very high	Lab proof of concept	Internal defect and texture analysis; porosity mapping	High cost, Radiation risk, low throughput, safety constraints
MRI	C2	Internal	Voxel	3–10 min/dataset	Sub-millimetre scale	\$150–3 M	Very high	Lab proof of concept	Moisture and fat mapping, microbial contamination detection	High cost, low throughput, safety constraints
THz-CT	C2	Internal, physicochemical	Voxel	5–600 + min/dataset	Sub-millimetre scale	\$120–500k+	Very high	Lab proof of concept	Moisture and density evaluation; foreign-body and package inspection	High cost, low throughput, water sensitive
Monocular Vision	C3	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	Up to 230 fps	Millimeter scale	\$0.2–2k	Low	Pilot instrument	On-site inspection, retail monitoring, consumer dietary assessment	Scale ambiguity, lighting sensitivity, limited accuracy
Binocular Vision	C3	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	Up to 120 fps	Sub-millimeter scale	\$0.5–5k	Medium	Industrial ready	Inline grading, fruit maturity evaluation, carcass geometry, consumer dietary assessment	Sensitive to textureless and specular samples, frequent calibration needed
Multi-View Vision	C3	Surface	Point cloud, mesh	Up to 230 fps	Sub-millimeter scale	\$2–30k	High	Pilot instrument	Offline inspection, high-precision morphology, defect analysis	High overlap required, costly computation, sensitive to texture feature
AI-driven reconstruction	C0	Depends	Point cloud, mesh, voxel, implicit	Sensor dependent	Adaptive	Depends	High	Lab proof of concept	Adaptive cross-stage reconstruction	Data-dependent performance, limited generalization

Note: *C1, C2, C3, and C0 represent high-throughput at-line reconstruction tools, high-resolution tomography and reconstruction tools, portable on-site reconstruction tools, and cross-stage AI-driven reconstruction, respectively.

** Spatial resolution levels are presented on a relative scale with micrometre < sub-millimetre < millimetre < centimetre. Actual values vary with system design and food type.

***Reference cost ranges are estimated and compiled from publicly available published list prices from 2020 to 2026, excluding taxes and installation.

****Typical computational load reference standard: Low (CPU ≤ 4-core; RAM ≤ 16 GB; No GPU); Medium (CPU = 6 – 8 cores; RAM = 16–32 GB; VRAM = 6–8 GB); High (CPU = 8 – 16 cores; RAM = 32–64 GB; VRAM 10–16 GB); Very high (CPU ≥ 16 cores; RAM ≥ 64 GB; VRAM ≥ 24 GB). Host-side computing footprint excludes sensor-embedded processing.

Abbreviations: CLSM = Confocal laser scanning microscopy; HSI = Hyperspectral imaging; LiDAR = Light detection and ranging; MRI = Magnetic resonance imaging; OCT = Optical coherence tomography; THz-CT = Terahertz computed tomography; ToF = Time of flight;

tools. Therefore, from both technological and practical perspectives, the following subsections are organised according to their deployment scale features along the food supply chain.

2.1. High-throughput at-line 3D reconstruction

High-throughput at-line 3D reconstruction techniques are primarily deployed on processing and sorting lines, enabling rapid, non-destructive quality inspection at an industrial scale, such as in sorting lines, packaging facilities, and processing plants. These methods strike a balance between inspection speed, reconstruction precision, and operational robustness, enabling the high-throughput evaluation of primarily external quality attributes, such as defects, contamination, geometric deviations, and compositional variations, during large-scale food handling operations.

2.1.1. Structured light imaging

Structured light laser imaging provides a non-destructive, high-resolution solution for food quality control, particularly for detecting appearance defects (Wang and Li, 2015), estimating volume (Lorentzen et al., 2021), and shape-based grading (Luo et al., 2023) at the raw material supply and manufacturing stages. The technique operates by projecting special textures or patterns, also called structured encodings, onto an object and analysing the surface deformation to reconstruct its shape (Bell et al., 1999). Two main projection patterns, namely triangulation-based and phase-based, are commonly employed in structured light imaging. The former employs striped, dotted, or colour-coded patterns to compute depth from the geometric relationships (Lorentzen et al., 2021), while the latter projects sinusoidal fringes and applies phase-shifting or Fourier profilometry to derive height from phase data (Yu et al., 2024). Phase-based methods generally provide higher accuracy and resolution but require multiple images and heavier computation, making them more suitable for high-precision quality evaluation and research applications. In contrast, triangulation methods enable faster processing and more straightforward implementation, making them suitable for broader industrial and dynamic applications. Despite their advantages, structured light techniques encounter challenges when applied to products with wet or reflective surfaces and to environments with complex illumination. The relatively high cost of industrial-grade equipment and calibration, together with inherent trade-offs between resolution and speed, restricts their current main application to high-value products, such as processed meat and seafood (Lorentzen et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2023).

2.1.2. Time-of-flight (ToF) methods

ToF methods, including ToF cameras and Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensors, rely on emitting the light pulse and measuring the time delay of the reflected signal to calculate distance, providing fast, non-destructive 3D sensing solutions increasingly applied to food quality control. ToF cameras capture depth images using 2D sensor arrays, offering millimetre-level resolution, high frame rates, and cost-effective operation for short- to medium-range inspection in controlled illumination environments. They have been applied to food quality control in the raw material supply, manufacturing, and distribution stages, which require high throughput but precise inspections, particularly for inline morphological inspection, grading, foreign body detection, and packaging verification. In contrast, LiDAR employs scanning mechanisms to generate sparse but accurate point clouds over longer distances, making it not only capable of at-line product quality sensing but also for medium to large-scale monitoring and management tasks in logistics, warehousing, and transportation to ensure the product safety (Nyalala et al., 2019; Saha and Zude-Sasse, 2022; Xie et al., 2023). Despite their advantages, ToF cameras are sensitive to ambient light and to the optical properties of food products, although they are generally more robust to light interference than structured light sensors. For example, high-reflectance or transparent packaging, as well as wet fruit

surfaces, can cause depth-sensing errors (Hong et al., 2024; Nyalala et al., 2019). Its limited sensing range also restricts its application in warehousing and transportation, where broader environmental coverage is required (Nisbet et al., 2024). Conversely, due to high costs and sparse data acquisition, LiDAR systems are not recommended for upstream raw material inspection or midstream processing stages demanding precise depth perception and high spatial resolution (Saha and Zude-Sasse, 2022; Xu et al., 2024). Overall, ToF cameras are better suited for high-speed, close-range quality control tasks on processing lines, while LiDAR excels in long-range sensing for products and the environment in supply chain logistics and warehousing, forming a complementary relationship between the two technologies.

2.1.3. 3D hyperspectral imaging (HSI)

3D HSI combines spatial, spectral, and morphological information, offering a non-destructive and rapid solution for food quality control. The ability of HSI to simultaneously capture both apparent geometry and invisible physicochemical properties makes it valuable for a wide range of applications in quality control across the supply chain, including automated sorting, process control, packaging evaluation, and logistics management (Gowen et al., 2007). Conventional HSI systems typically operate in the visible to mid-infrared wavelength range, and most acquire images from a single viewpoint, leading to incomplete spatial coverage and reduced robustness to occlusion (Ren and Sun, 2022). To overcome this limitation, recent research has integrated geometric 3D reconstruction into HSI to obtain more comprehensive information on product quality. For example, Ma et al. (Ma et al., 2021) employed a rotary conveyor with a fixed HSI camera to capture full-surface spectral data, while Song et al. (Song et al., 2024) developed a multi-mirror spherical-cap HSI system. Besides, Li et al. (Li et al., 2025) and Tayyab et al. (Tayyab et al., 2026) proposed rotational scanning strategies that enable simultaneous characterisation of chemical composition and 3D morphology. Although still in its early stages, these developments have significantly improved the reliability of HSI for food quality evaluation, including morphological shape, physicochemical attributes, and sensory texture. However, many current approaches remain constrained by batch-processing designs, which limit their suitability for large-scale, continuous evaluation applications. Current challenges include the substantial computational burden of high-dimensional spatial-spectral data, the high initial and maintenance costs of 3D HSI systems, and the unavoidable trade-offs between field of view, spectral accuracy, and spatial resolution. Looking forward, the miniaturisation of hardware, accelerated AI-based data processing, and advances in high-speed optical sensors are expected to facilitate the large-scale deployment of 3D HSI across food sorting, production, and distribution (Sun et al., 2024).

2.2. High-resolution 3D tomography and reconstruction

High-resolution 3D tomography and reconstruction are mainly laboratory-based techniques that emphasise high resolution and penetration, often relying on bulky, sophisticated instruments. Unlike surface-oriented 3D reconstruction techniques, tomography-based techniques can reveal subsurface and internal structures with high fidelity, enabling precise analysis of food microstructure. These techniques are mainly applied in mid-to-upstream supply chain activities, including raw material sorting, research and development, manufacturing, and distribution quality assurance.

2.2.1. Optical coherence tomography (OCT) and confocal laser scanning microscopy (CLSM)

Both OCT and CLSM are high-resolution optical 3D imaging tools primarily aimed at obtaining sample structural information at the sub-surface and microscopic scales. Such information mainly applied in tasks such as quality screening and sorting of raw materials (Ekramirad et al., 2024; Thampi et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2022),

packaging validation (Pan et al., 2022), quality control within processing and distribution (Li et al., 2015; Li et al., 2021), as well as optimization of formulations and processes (Jiang et al., 2022; Mhaske et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2018; Yang et al., 2022). OCT achieves non-destructive sub-surface body data acquisition based on low-coherence interferometry, which is suitable for identifying fine defects and contaminations in semitransparent or turbid samples (Fu et al., 2024; Huang et al., 1991), while CLSM obtains micrometer-scale 3D microstructures by stacking optical slices layer by layer, which can be enhanced with fluorescent labeling for the contrast of components such as proteins, fats, and starch particles, as well as spatial distribution of microorganisms and contaminants (Pankiewicz et al., 2015; Shamim et al., 2024). However, the deployment constraints could be the trade-off between resolution, depth of penetration, and high throughput. Besides, OCT is sensitive to vibration and environmental stability, and has high equipment maintenance and computational costs, while CLSM has a shallow depth of penetration, slow scanning, bulk system configurations, and often requires fluorescent staining. Therefore, they are currently more suitable for laboratory research, process mechanism analysis, and random sampling evaluation than for large-scale frontline online quality control tasks. In the future, with the decrease in cost of hardware, such as light sources and detectors, OCT and CLSM are expected to be first applied in high-value product and critical risk point monitoring, as well as research and development (R&D) and benchmarking scenarios (Ekramirad et al., 2024; Zhou et al., 2022).

2.2.2. X-ray computed tomography (CT) and magnetic resonance imaging (MRI)

Both X-ray CT and MRI are non-destructive 3D tomography tools for volumetric internal imaging. Rather than general-purpose online inspections, they are often used for analyzing product internal structure, high-fidelity benchmarking, and R&D tasks in the food supply chain. X-ray CT is widely regarded as one of the gold standards for internal non-destructive evaluation, and has been applied to identify internal defects, characterize porosity and texture, and achieve fine structural analysis through virtual optical slicing at fine structural detail up to the micrometer level (Li et al., 2015; Schott et al., 2023; Zennoune et al., 2022). Besides, MRI has non-ionization advantages and is good at characterizing water migration and fat distribution, monitoring textural changes and structural integrity, and microbial contamination (Bao et al., 2017; Caballero et al., 2017; Drissi et al., 2019). However, their deployment bottlenecks include the cost of expensive equipment, their bulky size, complex operation and maintenance, and low acquisition throughput, which limit their use in large-scale food supply chains for routine applications. In addition, X-ray CT requires radiation safety considerations, whereas MRI has relatively limited sensitivity to foreign objects such as metal, glass, and stones. Therefore, they are currently mainly used in laboratory and random sampling of high-value products, as well as in process and product development optimization, such as texture mechanism analysis, packaging and structural design, optimizing freezing, thawing, drying, and fermentation processing, and have the potential to be used in scenarios with higher safety and consistency requirements (Schott et al., 2023; Tempelaere et al., 2024).

2.2.3. Terahertz spectroscopy imaging computed tomography (THz CT)

THz CT is an emerging non-destructive, non-ionizing 3D inspection technology providing both penetration capabilities and spectral fingerprint information, which is potentially considered valuable in food quality and safety scenarios along the food supply chain, including raw material grading, foreign material and adulteration identification, and packaging integrity verification (Afsah-Hejri et al., 2019). Compared to traditional analysis tools that provide only structural information, terahertz waves are more sensitive to components such as moisture, sugars, and proteins, making them promising for simultaneously characterizing structural and some physicochemical attributes and enabling 3D visualization when combined with tomographic reconstruction (Ren et al.,

2023). However, the industrial deployment of THz CT still faces obvious bottlenecks, such as the strong absorption of water by terahertz that limiting penetration of highly water-containing food products, the scanning throughput that often struggles to meet the demand for online real-time detection, and the imaging sensitivity to environmental temperature and humidity, surface roughness, and trade-offs between resolution, speed, and system cost, raising the threshold of their scaled applications (Fu et al., 2024; Ren et al., 2023). Overall, THz CT is currently more suited as a complementary internal inspection and physicochemical characterization tool for laboratory studies and high-value scenarios, and its viability in the post-harvest supply chain is expected to increase in the future with the development of lower-cost transmitter and detector devices and faster imaging modalities (Fu et al., 2024).

2.3. Portable on-site 3D reconstruction

Beyond laboratory inspection that emphasises resolution and internal evaluation, and at-line sensing solutions that prioritise sensing efficiency and robustness, there is a growing need for flexible, low-cost, and portable 3D reconstruction food quality analysis approaches. Compared to upstream sorting and production stages, the downstream food supply chain, which mainly includes logistics, retail, and consumption, operates in diverse environments, constrained spaces and high real-time requirements. These stages usually lack the conditions for deploying complex or expensive sensing equipment, emphasising cost-effectiveness, deployment flexibility, and operational simplicity. Vision-based 3D reconstruction methods rely primarily on standard RGB cameras and advanced algorithms, making them ideal solutions for product and environment monitoring and management at low hardware cost, delivering scalable, efficient quality control.

2.3.1. Monocular 3D reconstruction and extensions

With the advantages of low-cost, non-destructiveness, and portability, monocular 3D reconstruction technique is suitable for tasks such as volume estimation, feature characterization, shelf monitoring, and consumption assessment, covering multiple sections within the food supply chain like sorting, logistics, retail, and consumption (Cao et al., 2024; Fang et al., 2015; Gao et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2024). Its high deployment flexibility enables integration into smartphones, fixed cameras, or embedded vision modules, combining low hardware requirements with high scalability. However, monocular approaches are naturally limited by scale uncertainty, missing depth information, occlusion and illumination sensitivity, and calibration drift, especially when dealing with irregular, reflective, and mutilated food targets. Their deployment often requires additional a priori or protocol constraints, such as controlled viewpoints, reference cues, and learned shape-scale constraints, to stabilize geometric evaluation results. Multi-view processing techniques like structure-from-motion (SfM) improve consistency and reliability through offline post-processing reconstruction, while simultaneous localization and mapping (SLAM) approaches are better suited for real-time position tracking and target reconstruction on consumer-grade mobile devices. Overall, monocular 3D techniques are suitable for in-situ monitoring and medium-precision decision support, while showing limited performance in scenarios such as heavily occluded structures, micron-scale defect analysis, or biochemical contamination assessment, and often require complementary sensing or multimodal fusion techniques.

2.3.2. Binocular vision and multi-view stereo (MVS)

Binocular vision and MVS, often supported by mature industrial hardware and algorithms, offer a practical compromise between monocular portability and high-end 3D sensing (Konstantakopoulos et al., 2021). Compared to monocular vision, binocular vision typically provides more stable scaling depth and stronger robustness, making binocular vision suitable for scenarios that require higher geometric

reliability, such as product sorting, package validation, and consumer-side quality assessment (Hsieh et al., 2021; Ivorra et al., 2015; Shi et al., 2025). MVS improves the reconstruction quality of point clouds and mesh models by introducing additional viewpoints, which is suitable for offline evaluation, documentation, and high-precision inspection workflows (Hong et al., 2024). Besides, MVS is often combined with SfM to form the SfM-MVS pipeline, and in practical deployment, common bottlenecks of MVS include sensitivity to dynamic lighting, complex calibration and maintenance requirements, and high computational burden and storage requirements. Besides, the accuracy of binoculars decreases significantly when the working distance increases, while MVS often requires more viewing angles and larger sensing space, more complex calibration and slower processing speed, making it difficult to be routinely used in high-speed production lines. Consequently, stereo vision is often suitable for near real-time applications with controlled geometry, while MVS is more suitable for offline quality assessment where completeness and traceability matter more than speed.

2.4. AI-driven 3D reconstruction

AI-driven 3D reconstruction represents a transformative direction for data-driven reconstruction of 3D structures directly from 2D images, improving reconstruction cost-effectiveness, automation, and adaptivity. In the food supply chain, such techniques offer promising potential to replace or complement expensive 3D sensing instruments, allowing high-throughput, non-destructive, and adaptive monitoring of product appearance quality and volumetric attributes. Traditional 3D reconstruction methods often struggle in practical food applications due to illumination variation, surface heterogeneity, product deformation, occlusion, and the time-consuming nature of geometric-based reconstruction (Hong et al., 2024; Shi et al., 2025). DL methods overcome these issues by learning 3D structures directly from 2D images or incomplete depth data, significantly reducing dependence on hardware constraints while improving adaptability to complex and heterogeneous food items. Although still at a very early stage of adoption in food research, AI-driven 3D reconstruction has demonstrated promise in early applications, such as portion estimation (Haroon et al., 2025), volume calculation (He et al., 2024), and appearance defect evaluation (Naritomi and Yanai, 2021). Current AI-driven 3D reconstruction methods can be classified into four major representation formats, namely voxel-based, point cloud-based, mesh-based, and implicit representation-based AI-driven 3D reconstructions.

Voxel-based representations model 3D objects as volumetric grids and are well-suited to 3D convolutional neural networks (3D CNNs) for subsequent quality-relevant analysis. This approach has been applied to estimate food volume and caloric content from single-view RGB images (Shao et al., 2023). Moreover, voxel-based deep models can naturally integrate with tomographic data such as X-ray CT scans, supporting internal defect detection and contamination analysis (Strafella et al., 2024). However, voxel grids require intensive computation and often suffer from low resolution, limiting their potential for deployment in large-scale and real-time inspections.

Point cloud-based methods reconstruct a set of unordered 3D points that efficiently describe object geometry, making them compatible with several existing 3D food quality analysis workflows (Xu et al., 2024). Haroon et al. (Haroon et al., 2025) proposed the VolE framework to reconstruct dense point clouds of food items from smartphone images, enabling lightweight portion estimation and labelling verification without camera calibration or dedicated depth sensors. Compared with voxel representations, point clouds offer improved memory efficiency, but their lack of explicit topology constrains surface-based analyses such as curvature or thickness estimation (Samavati and Soryani, 2023).

Mesh-based reconstructions generate continuous surfaces that accurately represent product geometry and texture. Such methods have potential for appearance-related safety evaluations and for visualising

quality control, such as seal integrity, surface defect detection, and cutting-path optimisation during processing. The “Hungry Networks” framework (Naritomi and Yanai, 2021) demonstrated early success by reconstructing dish models from a single RGB image for precise 3D food volume estimation. Mesh representations are memory-efficient and uniformly deformable, while their integration with DL architectures for intelligent quality evaluation remains challenging, and high-precision mesh reconstruction remains computationally expensive.

Implicit representation-based methods have recently emerged as a transformative approach for AI-driven 3D reconstruction, including Neural Radiance Fields (NeRF) (Mildenhall et al., 2021) and 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) (Kerbl et al., 2023). These methods model 3D objects as continuous functions that map spatial coordinates to occupancy, signed distance, or radiance, enabling smooth, resolution-independent reconstructions from limited or noisy input data. To the best of our knowledge, relevant research on food systems remains absent, although their ability to recover complex geometries suggests strong potential to improve the reliability and efficiency of quality control for future adoption, which will be further discussed in Section 4.

In addition, emerging AI-driven 3D reconstruction directions, such as point cloud completion (Blok et al., 2025) and multimodal fusion reconstruction (Liu and Chen, 2025), are enhancing the robustness and interpretability of AI-based inspection systems. Point completion aims to recover missing or occluded regions caused by overlapping food items and poor illumination, while multimodal fusion integrates complementary sensory inputs, such as RGB, hyperspectral, and depth cameras, to provide a more comprehensive and reliable quality evaluation. These approaches are still rarely applied in food research, yet they indicate promising pathways toward scalable, adaptive, and reliable intelligent quality inspection and control.

Overall, AI-driven 3D reconstruction marks a transformative shift from hardware-centric measurement to data-driven intelligent analysis, offering new opportunities for high-throughput, non-destructive, and adaptive food quality monitoring. Despite promising early progress, its broader implementation still faces challenges, including limited annotated datasets, insufficient model generalisation across product categories, and high computational resource demands. Overcoming these challenges will be crucial for enabling scalable, intelligent, and real-time 3D quality assessment across postharvest food supply stages.

3. Applications for 3D reconstruction in food supply chain quality management

Ensuring food quality and safety across the postharvest supply chain requires efficient, non-destructive, and reliable evaluation technologies that can adapt to diverse products and dynamic environments. 3D reconstruction techniques provide a unique bridge between physical quality sensing and digital decision-making, offering simultaneous insights into morphology, structure, and physicochemical composition. Unlike conventional computer vision-based quality inspection, which relies heavily on 2D imaging or spectroscopy inspection with limited captured viewpoints, shallow depth perception, insufficient spatial coverage, and sensitivity to environmental conditions (Ren et al., 2022). 3D reconstruction enables the volumetric characterisation of food products, including geometric, textural, and structural parameters that correspond directly to sensory and physicochemical quality indicators. When combined with DL and ML, these 3D data streams can be transformed into predictive insights for intelligent decision-making (Tempelaere et al., 2024). Generally, 3D reconstruction shows potential to enhance three key aspects of quality management, namely quantitative and non-destructive inspection by capturing complete geometry and internal quality details, process control and optimisation that enables feedback loops for dynamic manufacturing and distribution optimisation, and data-driven decision support and traceability that link reconstructed models with digital twins, IoT, and blockchain systems for

supply chain transparency and automation.

A comprehensive literature survey identified 90 high-quality studies on 3D sensing and reconstruction in the field of food science and technology, published between 2015 and 2025, primarily retrieved from the Web of Science databases. The corresponding quality management applications were subsequently classified into representative scenarios across key supply chain stages based on the main object of the research and the application scenario, including post-harvest processing (33 papers), food development and manufacturing (29 papers), product distribution (15 papers), and consumption assessment (13 papers). Each stage has different quality control objectives and faces unique challenges, such as product shape heterogeneity, occlusion, motion, illumination fluctuations, and cost constraints, which determine the choice of sensing and reconstruction techniques. For the product categories, Fig. 1 summarizes the relevant categories designed to avoid fragmented counting, and the counting is based on the appearance times of each product in the research. The results show that the most attractive products for 3D reconstruction are fruit and vegetable products (38%), followed by animal products of 18% (Fig. 1a-b). The results emphasize the suitability and potential benefits of 3D reconstruction for applications in fruit and vegetable products. Based on the statistic on different reconstruction methods, where the counts are based on the appearance times of each type of sensor from all research, X-ray CT remains the most prevalent 3D reconstruction analysis method for food products, given its capability for high-precision internal visualisation and external morphological analysis suitable for detailed food product quality evaluation, which is regarded as one of the golden standards for 3D visualisation evaluation (Fig. 1c-d). The detailed applications for different supply chain stages are analysed in sequence within the following sections, linking the technical advances of 3D reconstruction with their

implementation management.

3.1. Postharvest processing quality control

Postharvest quality evaluation constitutes the first and one of the most critical stages of quality management in the postharvest food supply chain. At this point, products are screened and graded based on their external morphology, internal structure, defect presence, and physicochemical properties, which determine their suitability for subsequent processing, distribution, and consumption (Song et al., 2024). To meet these diverse analytical demands, active 3D reconstruction techniques, mainly including structured-light imaging, ToF camera, LiDAR, X-ray CT, OCT, and MRI, have become dominant tools for non-destructive, high-precision inspection within this stage (Fig. 2a). Besides, relevant high-quality studies over the past ten years are summarized in Table 2, which collectively demonstrate how 3D reconstruction enables reliable postharvest quality evaluation across a wide range of food commodities.

3.1.1. External morphological evaluation and grading

Morphological features such as shape, size, and surface texture are key determinants of product grades and consumer acceptance, while manual grading and 2D image analysis are often limited by insufficient viewing angles, fluctuating illumination, and subjective human decisions, leading to inconsistent evaluation results (Xu et al., 2024). Relevant research pipeline generally first reconstructs the complete surface geometry represented as point clouds or mesh models, and then extracts geometric descriptors, such as length, diameter, volume, and surface area-to-volume ratio, which are then used for grading or combined with ML for quality prediction (Arendse et al., 2016; Luo et al.,

Fig. 1. Frequency (a) and percentage (b) of different food products investigated using 3D reconstruction-based food quality evaluation, and frequency (c) and percentage (d) of different 3D reconstruction methods adopted from 2015 to 2025. Abbreviations: X-ray CT = X-ray Computed Tomography; CLSM = Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy; ToF = Time-of-Flight; LiDAR = Light Detection and Ranging; SLS = Structured Light System; RGB = Red-Green-Blue; RGBD = Red-Green-Blue plus Depth.

Fig. 2. Percentage of different 3D reconstruction methods applied in the post-harvest food supply chain, including (a) post-harvest processing, (b) manufacturing stage, (c) distribution stage, (d) consumption stage, from 2015 to 2025, based on the main application scenario of each research. Abbreviation: CLSM = Confocal Laser Scanning Microscopy; LiDAR = Light Detection and Ranging; MRI = Magnetic Resonance Imaging; OCT = Optical Coherence Tomography; RGB = Red-Green-Blue; RGBD = Red-Green-Blue plus Depth; SLS = Structured Light System; ToF = Time-of-Flight; X-ray CT = X-ray Computed Tomography.

2023; Rogge et al., 2015; Xie et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2024). Relevant 3D sensing techniques such as RGB-D, ToF camera, structured light, LiDAR, and X-ray μ CT have been employed in the studies, where active optical 3D systems dominate in this area. These techniques achieve a good balance between speed and geometric accuracy, are easy to integrate into automated sorting lines, and typically yield millimetre-level estimation errors with high grading accuracies under production-line throughput (Hong et al., 2024; Xie et al., 2023). In detail, structured light is better at capturing fine geometric details but sensitive to reflections and illumination fluctuations. Besides, ToF and RGB-D tend to be more reliable in scenarios that emphasize robustness and high throughput (Luo et al., 2023; Xie et al., 2023). Meanwhile, multimodal fusion, like combining ToF and RGB with spectral or X-ray CT information, has also enhanced stability in complex scenarios (Wang and Li, 2015). However, hardware costs and calibration complexity remain deployment barriers, especially for scale-up applications in small and medium enterprises (SMEs) and low-margin product production (Xu et al., 2024).

3.1.2. Internal structure visualisation and quality analysis

Internal quality characteristics, including pore structure, porosity, and cellular morphology, can significantly affect product texture, taste, shelf life, and storage stability, while this information is difficult to obtain through surface inspection. Therefore, high-resolution 3D tomography reconstruction tools have been widely applied to quantitatively characterise microstructural heterogeneity and to correlate microstructure with product quality (Duan et al., 2020; Withers et al.,

2021). X-ray CT is the most widely used tool for volumetric internal visualisation of fruits, vegetables, and meats, with micrometre-scale structural characterisation for microstructural analysis and quality evaluation (Duan et al., 2020; Janssen et al., 2020; Wang et al., 2020; Withers et al., 2021). Additionally, other 3D tomography methods are usually selected based on the internal properties of the target products. For example, OCT is commonly used for non-destructive subsurface tissue mapping of high-value fruits such as kiwifruit and plums, where cell-layer information is correlated with firmness and water retention (Li et al., 2015; Zhou et al., 2021). Besides, MRI is good at characterizing the heterogeneity of internal components, particularly for analyzing moisture and fat distribution as well as contamination in meat and fish products (Bao et al., 2017; Caballero et al., 2017; Ho et al., 2019). In addition, the emerging THz-CT technique has been explored for analysing internal moisture and density differences in grains and seeds (Lei and Sun, 2023). However, the high equipment costs, time-consuming acquisition and processing, complex operation and maintenance, and potential radiation safety concerns make them difficult to be as routine online inspection tools in most supply chain scenarios (Withers et al., 2021). Consequently, their most effective role in current industrial practice could be as lab-based reference tools or benchmark standards for calibrating faster and more affordable optical or AI-driven reconstruction systems designed for in-line and at-line deployment. By establishing a ground-truth foundation for structural and compositional quality, these methods continue to guide the development of next-generation, high-throughput inspection technologies in raw material sorting in intelligent food supply chains.

Table 2
Representative applications of 3D reconstruction techniques for raw material quality evaluation and grading.

Product	Quality indicators	Sensor System	Technology/Algorithm	Overall Accuracy/Results	Reference
Carrot	Volume, length, maximum diameter	ToF camera	Poisson reconstruction	Registration error < 2.4 mm Morphological MAPE < 3%	(Xie et al., 2023)
Grape clusters	Grape cluster yield components, compactness, berry size, cluster volume, total weight, berries number	SVS	Delaunay triangulation SVM	$R^2 > 0.8$ for compactness and berry size, $R^2 = 0.82$ for volume, $R^2 = 0.83$ for total weight, $R^2 = 0.71$ for berries number	(Ivorra et al., 2015)
Sweet potato	Volume	LiDAR camera	Alpha shape method, Delaunay triangulation, Voxel-based volume integration, MLR, shallow neural network, deep neural network	Best volume estimation accuracy of 97.9%, $R^2 = 0.993$, RMSE = 9.5 cm ³	(Xu et al., 2024)
Oriental melons	Length, volume, density, morphological grade	ToF camera, stereoscopic camera	PCA, point cloud down-sampling, convex hull algorithm	$R^2 = 0.9676$, RMSE = 2.08 mm for length $R^2 = 0.9975$, RMSE = 3.77 cm ³ for volume $R^2 = 0.9057$, RMSE = 10.73 kg/m ³ for density Grading accuracy > 94%	(Hong et al., 2024)
Cherry tomatoes	Volume, mass	ToF camera	SVM, Bayesian artificial neural network	$R^2 > 0.92$ for all models	(Nyalala et al., 2019)
Horticultural products	Shape characteristics and surface geometry variations	X-ray μ CT, SLC	Elastic surface registration, PCA	Geometric registration error below 0.106 mm	(Danckaers et al., 2017)
Pomegranate	Internal structural components volume, length, diameter, peel thickness	X-ray μ CT	VG StudioMax software	R^2 values between 0.8 and 0.97	(Arendse et al., 2016)
Grape clusters	Cluster length, width, volume, compactness, and shape	Laser scanner	RAPIDFORM XOS software linear regression	$R = 84.5$ for cluster compactness estimation	(Tello et al., 2016)
Apples, pears	Volume, surface area to volume ratio, shape symmetry and variability	X-ray μ CT	Fourier descriptor algorithms, spherical coordinate transformation, covariance decomposition algorithm, NURBS surface fitting, PCA	error between 0.46% and 2.4%, 0.24% - 0.54% for volume and surface area to volume ratio	(Rogge et al., 2015)
Onions	Diameter, volume, weight, density, latent defects	RGB-D sensor, HSI, X-ray CT	vortex image calculation, linear regression	RMSE = 3.6 g (Weight), 1.7 mm (Diameter), 16.5 cm ³ (Volume), 0.03 g/cm ³ (Density), overall defect detection accuracy of 88.9%	(Wang and Li, 2015)
Milk powders	Surface roughness grades	MVVS	RealityCapture 1.0 software, SVM	Highest grading accuracy 87.5%	(Ding et al., 2023)
'Chili' pear	Internal pore structure characteristics	X-ray μ CT	VoxelStudio Max 3.0 software, FBP, feldkamp reconstruction	clearly and accurately distinguish internal organisation, size and location of cork spot	(Duan et al., 2020)
Braeburn apple	Internal pore structure characteristics	X-ray CT	Filtered back-projection, CTAn v1.17 software	3D connectivity of the pores could be clearly analysis	(Janssen et al., 2020)
Apple	Porosity, cell size, anisotropy, elongation, flatness, sphericity, object count, and pore surface density	X-ray μ CT, hyperspectral laser scattering imaging	Octopus reconstruction software, PLSR	R^2 of 0.89 for porosity and pore surface density	(Wang et al., 2020)
Landrace boar	Muscular and skeletal systems	X-ray μ CT	Parametric linear lagrange mesh, cubic Hermite meshes	84 muscles and 121 bones are included in the atlas	(Ho et al., 2019)
Kiwifruit	Cellular structures	OCT	Avizo 7.1 software	suitable for the processing of large data sets with acceptable accuracy	(Li et al., 2015)
Chicken egg	Yolk index, haugh unit, air cell height	Laser scanner	Triangulation modelling, multilayer perceptron neural network	$R = 0.97$ (yolk index), $R = 0.84$ (haugh unit) $R > 0.93$ (air cell height)	(Mollazade et al., 2021)
Sunflower seeds	Plumpness, kernel weight	THz CT	Inverse Radon transform	$R = 0.89$ (kernel weight)	(Lei and Sun, 2023)
Clove Pear	Volume, mass, surface bruise	HSI	Virtual volume intersection algorithm and texture technology	$R^2 = 96.18\%$ (volume) $R^2 = 98.18\%$ (Mass) Grading accuracy: 95.33%	(Song et al., 2024)
Atlantic herring	Nematode infections in fish	MRI	Multi-slice Spin-Echo imaging, three-dimensional GEImaging, ImageJ software	Accurately detect nematode accumulations and movement	(Bao et al., 2017)
Apple	Bruise volumes and morphological characteristics of damage	X-ray μ CT	FBP, multi-level Otsu's threshold method	$25 \pm 21\%$ relative error of traditional measurements	(Diels et al., 2017)
Apples	Concave features of stems, calyxes on surface, defects detection	MSI, SLC	triangulation method, standard spherical model	97.5% overall recognition accuracy	(Zhang et al., 2015)
Plums	Diameters, anisotropy, cell surface area, cell volume, cell amount, and mechanical injury	OCT	Watershed algorithm, morphological closed algorithm, AVIZO software	Early injury was acquired within 5–10 min	(Zhou et al., 2021)
Beef carcasses	Weight, conformation class, fat class	ToF camera	Halcon Image Processing Library MLR	R^2 of 70%, 50%, 23% for CCW, conformation, and fat class respectively	(Nisbet et al., 2024)
Eye round beef	Depth, three plane areas, surface area, volume, shear force, point cloud density, average planar index, average curvature	SLC	point cloud segmentation, descending sampling, alphaShape, ELM, SVR, linear regression	R of 0.8356, RMSEP of 11.1389, classification accuracy of 93.33%	(Luo et al., 2023)

(continued on next page)

Table 2 (continued)

Product	Quality indicators	Sensor System	Technology/Algorithm	Overall Accuracy/Results	Reference
Beef carcass	Curvature descriptor, volumetric descriptor, lean meat yield frame, height, volume, surface area, projected area of three planes, toughness, extensibility	RGB-D camera	Poisson mesh reconstruction, GPR, genetic algorithms	RMSE = 3.91%, R ² = 0.69	(Alempijevic et al., 2021)
Wheat dough	Spatial deformation, pH value, TVB-N	SLC	AlphaShape, OBB, PLSR, SVM, ELM	Rp of 0.9043, 0.8950 for toughness and extensibility	(Luo et al., 2023)
Beef eye-round	Moisture, lipid content, water activity, salt content, and color parameters	SLC	OBB, Alpha shape, PLSR, DTR, BPNN, SVR	Rp of 0.7669, 0.8388 for PH value and TVB-N	(Luo et al., 2023)
Pork loins	Mechanically separated poultry meat content	MRI	fractal algorithms, classical fractal algorithm, fractal texture algorithm, one point fractal texture algorithm, MLR, isotonic regression	R of 0.937, 0.902, 0.935 0.969, 0.978, 0.978, 0.936 for moisture, aw, salt, lipid, L, a*, b*,	(Caballero et al., 2017)
Cooked sausages		X-ray μ CT	NRecon software	Higher accuracy compared to traditional gravimetric and histological methods	(Nagdalian et al., 2021)

Abbreviations: BPNN = Backpropagation neural network; CLSM = Confocal laser scanning microscopy; DTR = Decision tree regression; ELM = Extreme learning machine; FBP = Filtered back projection; GPR = Gaussian process regression; HSI = Hyperspectral imaging; LiDAR = Light detection and ranging; MLR = Multiple linear regression; MRI = magnetic resonance imaging; MSI = Multispectral imaging; MVVS = Multi-view vision system; OBB = Oriented bounding box; OCT = Optical coherence tomography; PCA = Principal component analysis; PLSR = Partial least squares regression; SLC = Structured light camera; SVS = Stereo vision system; SVM/SVR = Support vector machine/regression; THz-CT = Terahertz computed tomography; ToF = Time of flight; X-ray μ CT = X-ray micro-computed tomography.

3.1.3. Defect detection and physicochemical property prediction

High-precision quality assessment of post-harvest raw materials is expanding beyond morphological and structural characterisation to decision-making tasks, such as defect detection and physicochemical attribute prediction. These studies usually combine 3D spatial geometric information, internal structural information, and complementary information, including spectral and deformation responses, and then transform them into functional metrics used by ML or DL models for automated grading and decision-making to support post-harvest raw material sorting and evaluation.

Defect detection can be regarded as an application extension of external and internal inspections, and such studies typically correlate geometric or volumetric cues with defect types such as mechanical damage, microbial infection, or foreign objects (Li et al., 2015; Song et al., 2024). Surface defects often require the fusion of optical 3D with additional contrast information to enhance sensitivity. For example, full-view 3D HSI enhances the identification of surface defects like bruises by integrating spectral features with 3D geometry (Song et al., 2024). Besides, OCT provides depth-resolved subsurface tissue information for the early detection of hidden damage in high-value plum fruit (Zhou et al., 2021). For deeper volumetric defects, tomographic imaging remains the most reliable source of internal inspection. X-ray CT has been applied to quantify bruise volume and physiological disorders in pears and apples (Fig. 4a; (Duan et al., 2020); (Diels et al., 2017)). In addition, MRIs have been shown to detect signals associated with biological contamination, such as parasites, in meat and fish products (Bao et al., 2017).

In addition to defect localisation, 3D reconstruction combined with learning models has been used to predict a range of product physical and chemical attributes, such as sensory texture, pH, TVB-N, and lean meat content, providing non-destructive alternatives to traditional physicochemical testing to support downstream grading, pricing, and shelf-life assessment. Current research is mainly based on volumetric imaging to extract proxy information, such as internal components, water content, surface geometry, and deformation response, combined with ML or DL model to infer corresponding functional qualities. For example, MRI coupled with fractal algorithms demonstrated the ability to establish good correlation with moisture-related indicators and colour attributes (Caballero et al., 2017). Meanwhile, structured light reconstruction combined with airflow-induced deformation has been used to estimate mechanical attributes like shear force, toughness, and extensibility of meat and dough products (Luo et al., 2023; Luo et al., 2023), and this approach has been further extended to predict chemical related freshness indicators through chemometric partial least square regression (PLSR) modelling (Luo et al., 2023). In carcass evaluation scenarios,

external 3D models reconstructed using structured light and ToF have also been used to predict lean meat yield and classify fat grade, achieving good correlation with reference values (Alempijevic et al., 2021; Nisbet et al., 2024). These examples demonstrate that AI-enhanced 3D model analyses bridge morphological analysis and functional quality prediction, providing a non-destructive alternative to conventional chemical assays to achieve more reliable product sorting and grading.

3.2. Food manufacturing quality control

The processing and manufacturing stage is critical to ensuring consistent product quality, production efficiency, and reducing material waste across industrial food production. 3D reconstruction offers powerful tools for understanding component interactions, optimising processes, and preventing defects by translating geometric and internal information into digital form for analysis. Unlike traditional single-point or 2D inspections, which provide limited information for instructing manufacturing, 3D methods capture complete volumetric data, supporting both research-level material design and process optimisation, as well as real-time industrial control. Among different 3D reconstruction methods applied within this stage, X-ray, CLSM and structure light system attracted intensity research over the past decade (Fig. 2b). This section discusses how 3D reconstruction contributes to both product development and intelligent process control, where in the former microstructure property relationships are quantified for formulation and processing optimization, and in the latter 3D data instruct predictive and autonomous quality management loops for the manufacturing system.

3.2.1. Product research and development

The goals of product R&D include improving nutritional quality, shelf-life, and sensory attributes by optimising formulation, processing, and packaging strategies. Across studies, the core value of 3D reconstruction in food R&D lies in transforming complex food matrix systems into quantifiable 3D structural descriptors, which could be further correlated with functional properties to support the development and validation of simulation models or digital twins in the manufacturing process. In relevant research, high-resolution tomography reconstruction techniques such as CLSM, X-ray μ CT, and 3D confocal Raman imaging are commonly used to quantify and characterize component distributions and interfacial phenomena, which can help research and development move from empirical trial-and-error to model-driven design (Gargiulo et al., 2020; Jiang et al., 2022; Mhaske et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2018). Confocal and fluorescence-based 3D information are often used to explain how microstructural organisation determines

macroscopic performance, thereby providing visual and quantitative evidence for R&D decisions, such as texture, stability, and optimisation of processing adaptation (Jiang et al., 2022; Mhaske et al., 2019; Wu et al., 2018). Related studies have also utilised spatial marker analysis to resolve microbial localisation or nutrient distribution, thereby informing packaging optimisation and enhancing food-safety-oriented product design (Mosquera-Fernández et al., 2016; Pankiewicz et al., 2015). X-ray μ CT provides characterisation of volumetric information such as internal porosity, air-cell connectivity, and density gradients, which contribute to the development of explanatory models of structure and properties and serves the process optimisation of different products and processes (Derossi et al., 2019; Ganju et al., 2024; Gargiulo et al., 2020; Miklos et al., 2015; Schoeman et al., 2016). In addition, other scales of 3D reconstruction routes have also demonstrated modelling value, such as cellular-scale 3D reconstruction for capturing fruit cells morphological evolution during ripening (Fig. 4b; Zhang et al., 2022), while access to irregular food-scale geometries can enhance the accuracy of process simulations, such as radiofrequency heating and support thermal homogeneity analysis and optimisation (Zhang et al., 2020). Despite their capability for high-resolution analysis, most of these techniques remain facing challenges of high equipment cost, system bulkiness, and slow scanning throughput. Their translation into high-throughput industrial R&D requires miniaturisation and algorithmic acceleration. The incorporation of AI for automated feature extraction and for correlating structure and property shows particular promise for overcoming these bottlenecks. ML models trained on large 3D datasets enable the identification of latent relationships between microstructure and macroscopic functionality, accelerating the iterative design of formulations and processing conditions. Finally, 3D reconstruction could transform food product R&D into a predictive, digitally traceable process, supporting intelligent manufacturing and reducing development time, costs, and bias.

3.2.2. Intelligent food manufacturing control

Beyond laboratory R&D, the deployment of 3D reconstruction in the manufacturing stage is shifting the quality management, moving from static spot-check inspections to more intelligent dynamic process monitoring and control. Currently, the most dominant application is to obtain time-series morphological information or internal microstructures to quantify product attributes like shrinkage, deformation, and texture-related structural changes that occur during processing, including drying, baking, heating, curing, and fermentation. Thereby, to provide actionable feedback for adaptive process control and to support the construction of smart manufacturing sensory layers for meat, horticultural, and semi-finished products production lines (Shamim et al., 2024; Simunovic et al., 2022; Vaskoska et al., 2020; Verdú et al., 2015). Active optical 3D sensing such as structured light and laser scanning are generally the more preferred online solution, as they strike a better balance between throughput rate and surface geometric characterisation capabilities, and also provides sufficiently reliable surface features for process control (Fig. 4c; Lorentzen et al., 2021); (Vaskoska et al., 2020); (Sun et al., 2023). Representative applications have also generally demonstrated that volume and shape changes from 3D reconstruction maintain strong correlations with weight loss, water migration, and other physicochemical process results, which might be reused across product categories (Lorentzen et al., 2021; Sun et al., 2023; Vaskoska et al., 2020). For in-depth mechanistic evaluation, high-resolution imaging techniques such as X-ray μ CT and MRI have provided insights into microstructural dynamics, including muscle fibre contraction, connective tissue changes, and pore evolution (Miklos et al., 2015; Schott et al., 2023). Given that common active optical systems achieve millimetre-level accuracy for online control while being sensitive to reflections and wet surfaces, and rely on stable calibration, whereas tomography systems provide micrometre-level evidence but are slow, complex, and costly (Sun et al., 2023; Verma et al., 2025). A practical strategy could be to integrate rapid surface scanning with periodic

high-resolution sampling for model calibration, enabling continuous process sensing at a reduced cost (Lorentzen et al., 2021; Schott et al., 2023; Xu et al., 2024). Further, integrating 3D reconstruction with AI analysis, IoT connectivity, and digital twin frameworks lays the foundation for smart manufacturing. The typical sensing-reconstruction-feedback loop is shown in Fig. 3, where continuous 3D data streams can be input to ML or DL models to identify deviations, predict process results, and link the control module to adjust parameters such as air speed, temperature, or conveyor belt speed to drive the production line toward self-optimization (Lorentzen et al., 2021; Luo et al., 2023). However, the scale-up bottlenecks could be related to the computational burden of 3D data processing, the complexity of system integration, deployment-level issues such as calibration drift and data latency, and fluctuations in raw materials and the environment that limit model generalisation. Adaptive algorithms and interoperability standards are needed to improve the migrability and robustness, while cloud-edge computing architectures could be the solution to minimise computational latency (Hong et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025; Nisbet et al., 2024; Protogeros et al., 2025; Song et al., 2024; Sun et al., 2023; Yu et al., 2024).

3.3. Product distribution quality control

The distribution stage primarily encompasses storage, transportation, and retail in the postharvest food supply chain, a critical stage in maintaining product quality and safety before it reaches customers. Food preservation strategies, including refrigeration, freezing, and controlled atmosphere (CA) techniques, are widely employed to extend shelf life and maintain product quality. During this phase, food materials could be exposed to fluctuations in temperature, humidity, and pressure, which can trigger chemical, physical, and microbial deterioration. Conventional inspection methods employed in storage and logistics environments primarily rely on environmental sensors, such as temperature probes and humidity detectors, along with occasional manual visual checks. However, these approaches provide only indirect or subjective assessments of product condition, without insight into internal structural or spatial variations (Ren et al., 2022); Liu et al., 2025a; (Ziani et al., 2025). In contrast, 3D reconstruction techniques enable volumetric, non-destructive, and information-rich evaluation, capable of capturing both product evolution and environmental heterogeneity across the entire distribution stage (Ge et al., 2024; Saha and Zude-Sasse, 2022; Tempelaere et al., 2024). Both X-ray CT and structured-light methods, as well as ToF-based sensors and RGB cameras, have been investigated for applications relevant to this stage. Although portable reconstruction methods like ToF-based and RGB cameras show great potential for practical use, they have received relatively few studies over the past decade (Fig. 2c). When combined with AI and simulation technologies, these methods support predictive and adaptive logistics management, enabling dynamic quality control throughout storage, cold-chain distribution, and retail monitoring.

3.3.1. Logistics quality management

Refrigeration, freezing, and controlled atmosphere (CA) are common preservation strategies used in the logistics chain. However, during prolonged storage and transportation, especially under fluctuating temperature or humidity conditions, moisture migration, shrinkage, and hidden internal disorders could lead to a decrease in product quality. Across studies, the critical applications of 3D imaging combined with ML or DL modelling in cold chain logistics are to achieve early, non-destructive identification of internal deterioration before it becomes visible, and also to quantify the microstructural changes associated with textural deterioration and storage stability risk. For fruits CA storage, tomography imaging such as X-ray CT combined with ML or DL models has demonstrated promising results in the early detection of internal browning, cavities, and physiological disorders (Tempelaere et al., 2024; van Dael et al., 2019; Van De Looverbosch et al., 2020), and the

Fig. 3. The conceptual framework on AI-enabled 3D reconstruction for postharvest supply-chain quality management.

research of Schut et al. (Schut et al., 2024) register the 3D scans with physical slices to achieve early, accurate identification and localisation of microstructural changes. In frozen logistics, a common quality concern is ice crystal size, its spatial distribution, and changes within products, which could be highly correlated with texture loss and thus important indicators for optimising the freezing process and controlling temperature fluctuations. X-ray μ CT-based 3D reconstruction has been widely used to visualise and quantify ice crystal formation, recrystallisation, and porosity and structural collapse, thus providing quantitative evidence for assessing damage due to improper freezing rates or temperature cycling and supporting the optimisation of cold-chain parameters and integrity safety control (Latil et al., 2022; Vicent et al., 2017; Zennoune et al., 2022; Zennoune et al., 2021). In addition, subsurface 3D characterisation can reveal the correlation between microstructural deformation and macroscopic hardness and cohesiveness under humidity variations, indicating that 3D reconstruction can capture early structural signals of quality drift in the logistics environment (Li et al., 2021). Overall, 3D reconstruction tools within the logistics stage are suitable as an internal auditing tool, an early-warning system for spot sampling, an aid to process optimisation and preservation schemes, and a model calibration tool rather than as a general-purpose online inspection solution. Its large-scale application still needs to consider the throughput, cost and deployment limitations in actual cold chain scenarios.

3.3.2. Quality control in storage and retail

In long-term and bulk storage scenarios, maintaining structural stability, airflow uniformity, and moisture control in stacks is critical to avoid uneven temperature distribution and spoilage. Across studies, 3D reconstruction is mainly used to translate storage configurations into quantifiable structural indicators, including stack geometry, porosity, and interparticle channels, which directly determine ventilation efficiency and localised microenvironment formation. Tomography reconstruction techniques have been used to reveal non-uniform airflow passages and temperature gradients inside the stack, and in combination with multi-physics field simulations, have provided the basis for optimising ventilation strategies and operating parameters. These optimisations aim to reduce the risk of localised overheating or condensation, thereby improving storage quality (Fig. 4d; (Ge et al., 2024)). In static environments such as warehouses and retail displays, driven by space constraints and the demand for low-cost, easy-to-deploy equipment, the primary function of 3D reconstruction tends to shift from internal quality inspection to environment-level mapping and regular monitoring. Portable RGB-D vision devices and LiDAR systems can be used to acquire geometric information at the shelf or aisle scale to support layout reconstruction, package deformation detection, and operations management. Studies have shown that monocular multi-view based reconstruction frameworks enable semantic and geometric alignment of shelf and object structures (Pathre et al., 2022), while vision-guided robotic stocking systems could be based on such geometric cues for display and placement operations (Peron et al., 2025). In terms of

Fig. 4. Representative visualizations of 3D reconstruction applications from (a) apple bruises under different pendulum impacts (Diels et al., 2017), (b) reconstruction of single cell morphological shape (Zhang et al., 2022), (c) potato slice morphological changes during drying (Sun et al., 2023), (d) the pressure distribution of the soybean grain pile in different directions (Ge et al., 2024), and (e) the nutrition assessment of the dish (Shao et al., 2023).

product-level quality evaluation in retail settings, combining LiDAR point cloud geometry with wavelength-specific reflectance intensity has also shown potential for contactless maturity monitoring and shelf-life prediction (Saha and Zude-Sasse, 2022). Recent work has also proposed the potential of aligning reconstructed 3D product models with template geometries for authenticity verification and traceability records, as well as continuous monitoring of display conditions, such as temperature and deformation, under a digital twin manner to enhance the reliability of supply chain quality management (Dong et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2025). Overall, storage and retail scenarios prefer scalable, high-throughput 3D object and environment-mapping and analytical tools for decision support. Deployments should focus on increasing adaptability to complex and occlusion scenarios, streamlining calibration and maintenance processes, and integrating with simulation or digital twin processes to enable actionable ventilation optimisation and shelf management decisions.

3.4. Consumption quality and nutritional evaluation

The consumer side is at the end of the post-harvest food supply chain, with the focus shifting from upstream quality monitoring and process control to individual-centred, personalised evaluation and health decision support. AI-driven 3D reconstruction tools show potential as an alternative to 24-hour dietary recall, which relies on memory and self-reporting, and could compensate for 2D computer vision tools in terms of accuracy and perspective (Lu et al., 2021; Shao et al., 2023). According to existing research, low-cost RGB passive 3D reconstruction tools account for the highest share, followed by RGB-D and structured-light devices (Fig. 2d), reflecting a preference for portable, affordable devices at the consumer end. By combining DL models with the obtained 3D data, such systems enable more scalable estimation of dietary intake and nutritional composition to support personalised dietary management (Fig. 4e; (Lu et al., 2021); (Shao et al., 2023); (Shi et al., 2025)). The trade-off between reliability and convenient use is an important consideration in current research. The binocular, ToF, and depth cameras typically provide robust portion estimates under real-world conditions (Dehais et al., 2017; Shao et al., 2023; Shi et al., 2025), while monocular solutions extend 3D portion estimation to more general cell phone and portable camera platforms, which are more reliant on a priori constraints and are sensitive to occlusion, illumination variations, and scene clutter (Fang et al., 2015; Gaikwad and Karwankar, 2019; Gao et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2024). As a result, monocular processes typically provide stabilised scale estimates through geometric modelling or container constraints and combine with ML or DL models for segmentation, recognition, and volume inference (Fang et al., 2015; Gaikwad and Karwankar, 2019; Gao et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2024). The system integrated with cell phones has also been validated for daily use in datasets and application scenarios, demonstrating its potential as a daily dietary recording tool (Konstantakopoulos et al., 2021). In dynamic acquisition with multi-view coverage, photogrammetry and SLAM methods support continuous or multi-frame volume estimation, while they remain susceptible to viewpoint gaps and motion noise in real dining scenes (Gao et al., 2018; Jia et al., 2024). From the deployment experience, missing information on occlusion and the diversity of food categories could be the most critical failures. As a result, the focus of AI-enhanced techniques is shifting towards improving generalisation capabilities under limited labelled data conditions, as well as enabling DL-based point completion networks of missing geometric structures (Lo et al., 2019; Lu et al., 2021). Overall, AI-enhanced 3D reconstruction is driving the end-to-end transformation of visual and memory-based dietary records into quantitative nutritional data to serve precision nutrition and smart health management. Future consumer-side systems are more likely to prioritise enhanced usage convenience and robustness, and to connect cloud-based 3D diet records with nutritional databases and digital twin diet simulators for continuous, data-driven monitoring at the individual level (Lu et al., 2021; Shao et al., 2023; Shi

et al., 2025).

4. Current challenges and future research directions

4.1. AI-enhanced multimodal fusion and interpretation

Due to the heterogeneous nature of food products, the single-modal reconstruction method usually struggles to provide stable, comprehensive, and unified product quality information (Fu et al., 2024; Hong et al., 2024; Ren and Sun, 2022). This challenge constrains the quality of digital 3D reconstruction models used in product quality control. Multimodal fusion technology has emerged as a key approach for developing robust, interpretable 3D reconstruction inspection systems (Singh et al., 2024; Song et al., 2024). Advancing systematic AI-driven fusion framework design could include sensor-level, feature-level, decision-level, and temporal data fusion strategies (Singh et al., 2024; Song et al., 2024). Sensor selection should be based on a fair comparison across modalities, such as at the matching operating point, encompassing target resolution, spatial coverage, acquisition speed, computational load, and unit cost, thereby achieving an economically justified fusion design. Despite the promising potential, the practical deployment of multimodal fusion techniques faces challenges, including data alignment errors, data drift, and insufficient interpretability. The deployment of fusion structure should be able to evaluate online alignment quality and modal quality, and degraded operation capabilities should be included when some modalities are missing to ensure the system maintains minimum acceptable performance. Besides, employing methods such as attention visualisation to trace cross-modal decision paths, and comparative studies are also necessary to evaluate the stability and performance of early fusion, late fusion, and hybrid fusion architectures across various supply chain conditions (Singh et al., 2024; Song et al., 2024). Therefore, short-term efforts should focus on developing robust cross-modal alignment algorithms under different food supply chain scenarios, while long-term goals may focus on establishing open, multimodal 3D food databases and standardised benchmarks to enhance algorithm reproducibility and interpretability.

4.2. 3D digital twin-based food traceability and authenticity

The integration of 3D reconstruction and digital twin technology holds the promising potential to fundamentally reshape traceability and authenticity management within the food supply chain (Fu et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2025). The 3D digital twin serves as a virtual representation of the physical product or environment, which can be continuously updated with 3D-reconstructed data and operation records (Arefi et al., 2026). When combined with AI analytics, IoT systems, and blockchain techniques, it enables closed-loop quality management, predictive quality control, and tamper-proof traceability (Lu et al., 2020; Protogeris et al., 2025). For instance, in cold chain logistics, product models captured using X-ray CT or ToF sensors can be linked to real-time temperature and humidity data to predict the risk of microstructural degradation or microbial contamination. Additionally, in the retail and consumption stages, the 3D morphology of selected products can serve as one of the digital fingerprints for comprehensive authentication. At the same time, geometric signatures anchored to blockchain records enable rapid and reliable anti-counterfeiting and origin verification within the food supply chain. However, implementing such systems faces several challenges, including that high-frequency 3D data collection could result in excessive communication load, synchronisation delays between edge and cloud devices could impact twin model accuracy, and standardised data exchange protocols between different layers remain lacking (Zhang et al., 2024). The dynamic evolution of food attributes needs real-time or frequent updates to geometric and physicochemical parameters in digital twin models. Future research could focus on developing compressed or parametric twin modelling for real-time edge deployment, as well as integrated verification mechanisms that

combine 3D morphology and chemical fingerprinting to enhance the robustness of authenticity detection.

4.3. Challenge on AI-driven 3D reconstruction

Despite the great potential of AI-driven 3D reconstruction for food supply chain quality management, its practical deployment is still at an early stage due to the high cost of equipment and computational requirements (Shi et al., 2025; Yu et al., 2024). Traditional high-fidelity 3D sensing and imaging systems are often confined to scientific research laboratories or high-value product applications due to their high cost, bulkiness, and computational burden (Antequera et al., 2021; Withers et al., 2021). Future research could focus on specific scenario categories, leveraging low-cost, affordable sensors and lightweight DL models to lower the threshold for real-time reconstruction and reduce the computational pressure of deployment (Balakrishnan et al., 2025; Liu et al., 2025). Besides, 3D data annotation and management are costly and difficult to scale. Compared with lab-based experiments, high-risk defects are rare in real supply chain scenarios, and such imbalanced label distributions can lead to high overall accuracy while overlooking critical defects. Applying self-supervised learning with active learning methods can effectively reduce labeling workload, while the data augmentation technique could reduce the imbalance in label distribution. In addition, Table 3 systematically summarises representative 3D reconstruction-related AI architectures over the past decade, highlighting the core strengths and limitations of corresponding models in the supply chain quality management, and proposes potential application hypotheses. The current lack of quality-related 3D data formats, interoperability standards, and benchmark datasets limits the scalability and regulatory acceptance of the proposed framework. To support interoperability, reproducibility, and authentication for scalable

deployment across scenarios, there is a need to develop collection parameters specifications and metadata for constructing open baseline datasets that cover different food sources and environmental conditions, and to establish mechanisms for model authentication and transparency (Protojeros et al., 2025; Xu et al., 2024; Yu et al., 2024).

4.4. Practical deployment in postharvest supply chains

Despite the promising potential of AI-enhanced 3D reconstruction, deploying these novel techniques from laboratory validation to large-scale industrial applications still facing challenge from the system aspects like environmental variability, time constraints, sensor stability, and model explainability, and from the sample aspect, such as variety, ripeness, moisture content, and surface optical properties (Fu et al., 2026; Singh et al., 2024; Xu et al., 2024). These practical limitations could lead to performance degradation or even failure in real-world deployment in different supply chain scenarios. Future research validation would not only demonstrate conceptual feasibility but also involve mid- or large-scale verification. Besides, the computation efficiency, data throughput, and system integration are also critical for system deployment. 3D reconstruction and multimodal perception could significantly increase computational and transmission burdens, while a high-latency system might not be able to form a closed-loop control system and meet the requirements of different quality evaluation tasks. The application of a cloud-edge computing architecture could reduce the computational and transmission burdens, thereby lowering system latency (Balakrishnan et al., 2025). At last, the explainability and regulatory acceptance are also critical considerations. Prediction model outputs should be integrated into existing quality assessment or HACCP processes to trigger management actions, and the system should record run details, including model versions, threshold settings, and decision

Table 3
Representative AI-driven sensor-based 3D reconstruction models over the past 10 years and their potential applications in postharvest food supply chain management.

Model	Input	3D representation	Advanced features	Key drawbacks	Applications hypotheses	Reference
3D-R2N2	Single/Multi-view RGB	Voxel Occupancy	Reconstruct coarse volumetric geometry from few views, useful for bulk volume estimation	Low resolution, cannot recover the fine details of products	Distribution: coarse reconstruction for pallet and carton volume estimation to optimise space utilisation Distribution: rough box/pallet volume estimation, stacking simulation	(Choy et al., 2016)
PSGN	Single RGB	Point Cloud	Directly predicts point sets from an image with fast target shape estimation	No topology, sparse points, poor for fine inspection	Retail: coarse 3D shape for picking simulation from e-commerce images	(Fan et al., 2017)
PointNet	Point Cloud	Point Cloud	Efficient large-scale point cloud processing, suitable for product, shelf, and pallet detection	Lacks local geometry awareness, fine defects could be missing	Distribution: shelf recognition, pallet occupancy prediction, stock safety monitoring	(Qi et al., 2017)
PointNet++	Point Cloud	Point Cloud	Strong local feature extraction ability, useful for complex scenes	Slower inference, limited real-time processing application	Distribution: complex warehouse scene analysis, goods & worker detection	(Qi et al., 2017)
Pixel2Mesh	Single RGB	Triangle mesh	Directly produce continuous surface mesh from products, suitable for product surface inspection	Relies on initial ellipsoid topology, limited to varied product packaging	Production: detailed single-item reconstruction for defect inspection Retail: product visualisation for marketing assets	(Wang et al., 2018)
DeepSDF	Point samples with SDF	Implicit continuous SDF	Builds high-precision standard models to support shape defect detection	Slow optimisation, limited scalable potential for mass real-time inspection	Production: reference model library, packaging deformation detection	(Park et al., 2019)
NeRF	Multi-view RGB, camera poses	Implicit radiance field	High-fidelity reconstruction, novel view synthesis reveals hidden defects	Computationally expensive, sensitive to view coverage	Production: defect inspection from new viewpoints Retail: virtual product visualisation	(Mildenhall et al., 2021)
OccNet	Multi-view RGB + temporal features	Dense semantic voxel occupancy	Provides full-scene occupancy, supports storage planning	High computation and annotation cost, less accessible to SMEs	Distribution: warehouse aisle occupancy detection, AGV route planning Production: real-time surface defect and deformation detection	(Tong et al., 2023)
Gaussian Splatting	Multi-view RGB	3D Gaussian distribution rendering	Real-time high-quality reconstruction, suitable for online inspection and monitoring	Heavy memory requirement for dense scenes, limited dynamic support	Distribution: digital twin in cold-chain, warehouse and factory	(Kerbl et al., 2023)

logs, to support auditing and regulatory requirements.

5. Conclusions

The combination of 3D reconstruction and AI techniques is reshaping the food supply chain quality management system, moving it from an intermittent, manual inspection to a continuous, adaptive, data-driven assessment framework. By correlating external morphology, internal microstructure, and physicochemical 3D distribution with product quality attributes, AI-driven 3D reconstruction analysis enables accurate quantitative and sorting assessment throughout post-harvest processing, manufacturing, distribution, and consumption. It was found that although active optical and tomographic imaging systems can achieve high-precision measurements, their scalability and cost-effectiveness remain limited. Large-scale applications need to rely on artificial intelligence-driven low-cost adaptive sensing solutions to ensure stable operation in dynamic environments and industrial conditions. This paper also highlights the potential of multimodal fusion and digital twins for AI-driven 3D reconstruction-based quality control and authenticity verification, and points out that the lack of annotated datasets, equipment complexity, computational burden, standardization, and regulatory issues needs to be addressed for practical deployment. By integrating technological, analytical, and managerial perspectives, this review positions AI-enhanced 3D reconstruction as a foundational enabler of next-generation management of food safety, authenticity, and sustainability across the global postharvest supply chain.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The authors are unable or have chosen not to specify which data has been used.

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